
Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following guidelines and style:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were *or* Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in ...
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the IRRN should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common — not trade — names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in IRRN contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Two promising rice cultivars for irrigated systems in Bihar, India

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Two promising lines from Bangladesh were identified in 1976 at the Agricultural Research Institute, Patna, from the International Rice Yield Nursery. The lines BR51-46-5 and BR51-91-6, are sister selections from the

cross IR20/IR5-114-3-1. Both lines have medium growth duration (135-140 days). They are intermediate in height, nonlodging and are suitable for irrigated transplanted areas. BR51-91-6 also performs well under rainfed-lowland fields. Both are moderately resistant to bacterial blight in the field.

The two lines have given consistent yields during the past 4 years (see table), and have been proposed for a minikit test program during 1981 (wet season) kharif in Bihar. ■

Performance of BR51-46-5 and BR51-91-6 at different sites in Bihar during the wet season, 1976 to 1979.

Site	Year	Yield (t/ha)			
		BR51-46-5	BR51-91-6	Jaya	Sita
Patna	1976	5.2	4.9	—	4.2
	1977	6.8	6.0	4.5	5.8
	1978	6.0	6.0	4.5	5.1
	1979	5.4	5.0	3.7	3.6
Pusa	1977	3.8	4.6	3.2	2.4
	1978	4.1	3.3	3.8	3.6
	1979	3.4	3.2	3.2	3.1
Bikramganj	1977	8.7	9.0	7.1	7.8
	1978	4.4	5.4	—	4.3
	1979	6.7	7.5	7.2	7.7

Method for mass-rearing the rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis*

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Although the rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* is widely distributed as a pest of rice in Asia, little is known about its ecology and control. The larvae of this pyralid moth possess tracheal gills and require water for survival. Damage is caused by the leaf-feeding larvae, which cut the tips of rice leaves to make tubular cases. Larvae float on the water surface in their cases during the day and at night climb up the rice plant and feed on leaves by scraping the leaf tissue and

leaving white skeletonized feeding marks. Fields are infested only during the vegetative stage, from seeding to maximum tillering.

Larval populations are often highly aggregated because water currents passing through paddies cause them to float downstream to lower-lying fields. This aggregative behavior has complicated chemical control trials and little is known about the effectiveness of various insecticides against this pest. Identification of possibly resistant cultivars has been hampered by lack of a rearing method for producing adequate numbers of caseworms for greenhouse screening.

A mass-rearing method was developed to produce caseworms for insecticide